

RS-006-WP2

Prototyping Lab Services – UC09

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1. Document Overview

Objectives

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR1) for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

This document is the Proposal for the Analysis Phase of the MarketPlace for Work Package 2 (DCS).

Applicable documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[A1]	16/10/2024	VERBALE DI AVVIO ANTICIPATO DELL'ESECUZIONE DEL CONTRATTO PER IL SERVIZIO SERVIZI PER LA CREAZIONE, IL MANTENIMENTO E L'INSTALLAZIONE DI SOFTWARE E SERVIZI ICT DI RICERCA CUSTOMIZZATI – "SOFTWARE LAB", CUP B53C22001770006, CIG B20BDCF4C9, PROT. 167440/2024 DEL 16/10/2024
[A2]	20/06/2022	D.D. n. 11 del 20/06/2022 - a valere dell'avviso pubblico per il "Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca" finanziato nell'ambito PNRR Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1, per la tipologia di intervento i. potenziamento di IR presente nel PNIR a priorità alta nell'ambito dell'area ESFRI "Social and Cultural Innovation e contestuale disposizione di impegno di spesa – CIG: B20BDCF4C9"

Table 1 - Applicable Documents

All documents mentioned in this list are available in the Document Repository, section "Applicable Documents".

Reference documents

Reference documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement and Project scope, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[R1]	20/06/2022	D.D. n. 11 del 20/06/2022 - a valere dell'avviso pubblico per il "Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca" finanziato nell'ambito PNRR Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1, per la tipologia di intervento i. potenziamento di IR presente nel PNIR a

		priorità alta nell'ambito dell'area ESFRI "Social and Cultural Innovation e contestuale disposizione di impegno di spesa – CIG: B20BDCF4C9"
[R2]	16/12/2024	RS-006-WP2
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Table 2 - Reference Documents

Acronyms

A list of acronyms frequently used in this document.

Term	Definition
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ITSERR	Re-Inforcement project for the RESILIENCE Research Infrastructure for Religious Studies Research
WP	Work Package
LoRA	Low Rank Adaptation
SimCSE	Simple Contrastive Learning of Sentence Embeddings
BPE	Byte-Pair Encoding
PEFT	Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning
SSM	State Space Model

Table 3 – Acronyms

2. Project Context and Introduction

The central aim of this use case was a research-focused attempt to test a critical hypothesis: could the Mamba architecture, a recent and highly efficient *State Space Model*, serve as a viable and effective alternative to mainstream Transformer models for the complex task of semantic retrieval in ancient languages? While Transformers have demonstrated immense power, their quadratic scaling costs present challenges. This investigation sought to explore whether *Mamba's* linear-time processing and selective-state mechanism could be successfully adapted to a niche, morphologically rich domain for which it was not originally designed.

The project was therefore not merely an engineering task, but an empirical study to determine if this newer architectural paradigm could be specialized to produce high-quality, nuanced sentence embeddings for historical texts, potentially offering a more computationally efficient path to state-of-the-art performance in specialized linguistic domains.

2.1 Introduction to State Space Models (SSMs)

While Transformer models have dominated natural language processing, they face computational challenges with very long sequences. *State Space Models*¹ represent an alternative and highly efficient architecture. Inspired by control theory, *SSMs* process sequences linearly, allowing them to handle extremely long contexts with significantly lower computational and memory requirements. The *Mamba*² architecture is a recent, high-performing *SSM* that uses a selection mechanism to dynamically focus on relevant information, making it a powerful candidate for deep linguistic analysis.

3. State of the Art and Initial Exploration

3.1 The Mamba Architecture

Mamba's strength lies in its selective *SSM* core. Unlike Transformers that use quadratic-cost self-attention to relate all tokens to all other tokens, *Mamba* maintains a compressed "state" and updates it token-by-token. Its key innovation is a data-dependent mechanism that allows the model to selectively forget irrelevant information or retain long-range dependencies as needed, combining the efficiency of recurrent models with the performance of Transformers.

3.2 Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT)

Fine-tuning large models is computationally expensive. *Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning*³ (PEFT) methods adapt models by training only a small fraction of their parameters. *Low-Rank Adaptation*⁴ (LoRA) is a prominent PEFT technique that freezes the pre-trained model's weights and injects small, trainable low-rank matrices into its layers. This allows for significant adaptation with minimal computational overhead, making it an ideal strategy for efficiently specializing large models for new tasks.

3.3 Sentence Embedding Generation: From Tokens to a Single Vector

A language model like *Mamba* operates at the token level, producing a contextualized vector representation—or *hidden state*—for every token in an input sentence. However, for semantic retrieval, a single vector representing the entire sentence is required. To achieve this, we employed **mean pooling**, a standard and robust technique for aggregating token-level information into a sentence-level embedding. The process is as follows:

1. **Obtain Hidden States:** A sentence is passed through the model, which outputs the final layer's hidden states—a sequence of vectors, one for each token.
2. **Apply Attention Mask:** To handle batches of sentences with varying lengths, shorter sentences are padded with special tokens. These padding tokens do not contribute to the sentence's meaning and must be ignored. The model's *attention_mask* is used to identify only the real, non-padding tokens.
3. **Calculate the Average:** The hidden state vectors corresponding to the real tokens are summed together, and the result is divided by the number of real tokens.

Figure 1 visually represent the above mentioned process.

Figure 1 – Sentence Embedding Generation Schema

This operation effectively computes the average of all meaningful token vectors in the sentence, producing a single, fixed-size sentence embedding. This vector captures the overall semantic meaning of the sentence and is the final representation used for similarity calculations (e.g., *cosine similarity*) in the *Gretino* dataset.

3.4 Initial Exploration and Rationale for Adaptation

Before committing to a comprehensive adaptation process, we evaluated several resource-efficient strategies to determine if the base model could be leveraged with minimal modification. These preliminary investigations were crucial, as their outcomes provided a strong empirical justification for the more in-depth, phased approach ultimately adopted.

3.4.1 Cross-Lingual Translation Approach

As an initial hypothesis, we investigated whether the language barrier could be overcome by translating the Latin benchmark into English and exploiting the base *Mamba* model's strong native capabilities in that language. To test this, we translated the 100 query sentences and 500 candidate targets from Latin into English and evaluated the model using the *Gretino* retrieval pipeline. The approach achieved an average score of **2.97/5** for retrieving relevant sentences within the top 10 results—noticeably higher than the **2.09/5** obtained by the unmodified *Mamba* base model when evaluated directly on the original Latin queries. While this pragmatic shortcut provided a working baseline, it also exposed the limitations of current translation tools for specialized historical texts: essential grammatical subtleties and morphological features were often lost, reducing semantic fidelity. These findings underscored the necessity of processing the material in its original language to achieve reliable retrieval performance.

3.4.2 Direct Tokenizer Modification

A second line of investigation explored whether the model's pre-trained knowledge could be transferred by directly altering its tokenizer. The hypothesis was that if we could map new Latin tokens to existing English tokens with similar meanings, we could effectively inherit the pre-trained embedding vectors, bypassing a costly retraining phase. Starting from the original *Mamba* base vocabulary, we constructed a Latin-to-English mapping using a large *Wiktionary-derived dataset*⁵. Each Latin lemma was paired with an English equivalent: when available, we extracted keywords from the dictionary description; when no description was provided, we supplemented the mapping with Google Translate. The resulting intermediary set of pairs was then aligned with the English lemmas in the original tokenizer. To achieve this, we applied text-distance algorithms, using the *Dice similarity*⁶ coefficient at different thresholds to identify high-confidence matches between existing English tokens and their Latin counterparts.

Tokenizer Merge Logic Modification: Beyond simply swapping vocabulary items in the *vocab.json* file, we also attempted to modify the tokenizer's *merges.txt* file. This file is critical as it defines the *Byte-Pair Encoding*⁷ (BPE) rules that instruct the tokenizer how to combine subword units into larger, meaningful tokens (e.g., how to merge "walk" and "ing" into "walking"). By attempting to align these merge rules with the new Latin vocabulary, we sought to make the tokenization process more coherent for the target language.

Using this modified tokenizer, we benchmarked the unaltered *Mamba* model on *Gretino*. Table 4 reports the retrieval performance across thresholds. While the highest score achieved was **2.00/5** (at 88–88.5% similarity), overall results fluctuated around this value and frequently fell below the original baseline (2.09/5).

Threshold (%)	80	85	87.5	88	89	90	92	98
Score (n/5)	1.48	1.62	1.99	2.00	1.94	1.94	1.88	1.98

Table 4 – *Gretino* Score Direct Tokenizer Modification

This experiment yielded a key methodological insight: a model's semantic understanding is tightly bound to the learned embedding vectors associated with each token ID, not merely to the surface form of the token string. Simply swapping tokens in the tokenizer file proved insufficient for transferring meaningful representations to a new language.

These findings confirmed that effective adaptation requires retraining the embedding layer on the new vocabulary, rather than relying on direct tokenizer edits.

Taken together, these two exploratory paths—translation-based evaluation and direct tokenizer modification—provided valuable insights but fell short of delivering robust performance. These lessons directly motivated the more principled, domain-aware strategy developed in Chapter 4, where the tokenizer, embeddings, and fine-tuning objectives were systematically aligned with the characteristics of ancient languages.

4. Work Performed: A Phased Approach

The project was executed in two distinct phases to systematically adapt the *Mamba* model to the target domain. In Figure 2 we can observe a visual representation of the overall process.

Figure 2 – Phased Approach Schema

4.1 Phase 1: Foundational Model Adaptation

The first adaptation phase focused on equipping the base *Mamba* model with the fundamental vocabulary of ancient languages. This stage was not yet task-specific fine-tuning, but rather a preparatory step designed to align the model’s internal representation space with the linguistic properties of Latin. It consisted of two main procedures:

4.1.1 Tokenizer Expansion

The original Mamba tokenizer was trained on modern, English-centric corpora and lacked coverage for Latin morphology. To address this gap, we extended the tokenizer by training a temporary *BPE tokenizer* on a large Latin corpus. The new vocabulary was merged with the original tokenizer, adding previously unseen Latin lemmas while preserving compatibility with the pre-trained model. This ensured that the model could properly recognize and tokenize the morphological richness of the target language.

4.1.2 Embedding and Output Layer Retraining

Once the tokenizer was extended, we adapted the model’s input and output interface to the new vocabulary. Specifically, we **retrained only the token embedding matrix and the output (*lm_head*) layer**, while freezing all other parameters of the *Mamba* model. This choice was motivated by two considerations:

- Freezing the core model preserved its strong sequence modeling capabilities while keeping training computationally feasible.
- The embeddings and output layer directly map token IDs to semantic vectors; without retraining, the newly introduced Latin tokens would remain meaningless within the model’s vector space.

We explored multiple learning rate configurations before converging on a setup where the embedding and output layers were optimized separately with slightly different learning rates. A cosine learning rate schedule with warmup was adopted to stabilize training, and evaluation against the *Gretino* dataset was integrated into the training loop to continuously track semantic retrieval performance.

The embedding layer was trained using a carefully selected set of hyperparameters to ensure stable and effective learning. In particular, the training was configured with:

- **learning rate embedding layer: 1.0×10^{-3}**
- **Learning rate output layer: 7.5×10^{-4}**
- **batch size: 32**
- **Epochs: 10**
- **Maximum Sequence Length: 1024**
- **Optimizer: AdamW with cosine learning rate schedule**
- **Warmup ratio: 50%**

The total training process for this phase was executed on an *NVIDIA H100 GPU* and produced multiple checkpoints, of which the **best-performing checkpoint was selected based on Gretino dataset evaluation**. This configuration provided the most stable convergence and was retained as the foundation for the subsequent fine-tuning phase.

This foundational phase did not yet aim to optimize the model for semantic similarity, but rather to prepare it for the **task-specific fine-tuning with LoRA and SimCSE** described in Phase 2. By the end of Phase 1, the model was capable of properly handling Latin input, providing a solid basis for the contrastive learning objective applied in the subsequent stage.

The benchmark results of this foundational phase are presented and analysed in Chapter 5.

4.2 Phase 2: Advanced Fine-Tuning with LoRA

With a solid foundation, we proceeded to task-specific adaptation using the *LoRA fine-tuning* technique.

- **Adoption of LoRA:** Recognizing the need for a parameter-efficient approach, we adopted *LoRA* to adapt the *Mamba* model. This strategy targets the linear projection matrices within the Mamba architecture (*in_proj*, *out_proj*, etc.), using *low-rank decomposition* for efficient updates while keeping the vast majority of the model's parameters frozen.
- **Implementation:** We utilized the *PEFT library* to implement the *LoRA adapter*. The training pipeline was structured in a modular repository, with distinct modules for configuration, data handling, and a custom evaluation callback to monitor performance on our specific retrieval task.
- **The Unsupervised SimCSE Training Objective:** The fine-tuning process was driven by an unsupervised *SimCSE*⁸ (Simple Contrastive Learning of Sentence Embeddings) objective. This method is particularly powerful because it does not require labeled data (e.g., manually annotated pairs of similar sentences).
- **Core Principle:** *Contrastive Learning*, the fundamental goal of *SimCSE* is to refine the embedding space such that semantically similar sentences are pulled closer together, while dissimilar sentences are pushed further apart. This is achieved by training the model to distinguish between "positive pairs" (sentences that should have similar embeddings) and "negative pairs" (sentences that should have different embeddings).

- **Unsupervised Pair Generation:** The key innovation of unsupervised *SimCSE* is how it generates these pairs. A positive pair is created by feeding the exact same sentence through the model twice within the same training batch. Because neural networks, particularly during training, utilize dropout layers that randomly deactivate neurons, the two resulting embeddings will be slightly different but semantically identical. This creates a perfect positive pair without any need for external data or labeling. All other sentences within the same training batch are treated as negative pairs relative to the original sentence.
- **Training Process:** Our implementation followed this principle directly. For each training step, our custom data collator took a batch of sentences and duplicated each one. The model then generated embeddings for this expanded batch. A custom loss function was then used to calculate a similarity matrix (using cosine similarity) between all embeddings. The training objective was to maximize the similarity score for the positive pairs (a sentence and its dropout-varied duplicate) while minimizing the scores for all negative pairs. A temperature parameter was used to scale the similarity scores, controlling the difficulty of the task and helping the model learn a more discriminative embedding space.

The fine-tuning phase required careful hyperparameter selection to balance convergence stability with the strict training time constraint. We experimented with different **learning rates** and **temperature values** for the *SimCSE* objective, ultimately identifying the configuration that yielded the best-performing checkpoint on Gretino evaluation.

The final training was conducted on an **NVIDIA H100 GPU** with gradient checkpointing and memory-optimized settings, running for **3 epochs** over the Latin literature dataset. The key hyperparameters were:

- **Learning rate: 3×10^{-5}**
 - **Warmup Ratio: 0.05**
 - **Batch size: 128 (with gradient accumulation steps = 2)**
 - **Max sequence length: 256**
 - **Temperature: 0.15**
 - **Optimizer: AdamW with cosine learning rate schedule and 0.01 weight decay**
 - **Precision: bfloat16 (H100-optimized)**
- Training time: capped at 5 days (≈ 120 hours)**

This setup produced the most stable and discriminative embedding space, as confirmed by benchmark evaluation. The resulting checkpoint was retained as the final model for semantic retrieval tasks.

The benchmark results of this fine-tune phase are presented and analysed in Chapter 5.

5. Results and Evaluation

5.1 Benchmarking Methodology

Model performance was evaluated using the **Gretino Dataset**, designed for sentence-level semantic retrieval in Latin.

The benchmark consists of **100 query sentences** and **5 correct target phrases** associated with each query, resulting in a **total pool of 500 target sentences**.

The evaluation procedure, for each of the 100 queries, embeds all 500 target sentences and rank them by semantic similarity. The primary success metric is the model's ability to rank the 5 correct targets for a given query as highly as possible. Performance was measured by the average number of correct targets successfully retrieved in the top 10 results (**Hits@10**).

5.1.1 Foundational Model Adaptation

In Phase 1 we prepared the base model for Latin by

- **Extending the tokenizer** with lemmas learned from a Latin corpus
- **Retraining only the token embedding matrix and the output (lm_head) layer**, keeping all other Mamba weights frozen.

This aligns token IDs with meaningful vectors in the new vocabulary and serves as a prerequisite for the *LoRA + SimCSE* fine-tuning in Phase 2.

Training checkpoints were periodically evaluated on the *Gretino* retrieval benchmark. We report **training loss** (proxy for optimization progress) and **avg_hits@10** (task relevance) across steps.

We ran three single-LR baselines where the embedding and output layer shared the same learning rate. Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows respectively the Training Loss and Average hits on gretino while retraining the model with a learning rate of $1.5e-5$, Figure 5 and Figure 6 show Training Loss and Average hits for the retraining with a learning rate of $2.5e-5$ and Figure 7 and 8 shows the Training Loss and Average Hits using a learning rate of $5e-5$.

- (Model 1) LR = $1.5e-5$

Figure 3 – Training Loss ($1.5e-5$)

Figure 4 – Average Hits @10 ($1.5e-5$)

- (Model 2) LR = 2.5e-5

Figure 5 – Training Loss (2.5e-5)

Figure 6 – Average Hits @10 (2.5e-5)

- (Model 3) LR = 5e-5

Figure 7 – Training Loss (5e-5)

Figure 8 – Average Hits @10 (5e-5)

As mentioned in the previous section, the **best checkpoint** was obtained when **decoupling the learning rates: 1.0×10^{-3} for the embedding layer and 7.5×10^{-4} for the output layer**, with AdamW + cosine schedule, batch size 32, max seq length 1024, and periodic Gretino evaluation. It is possible to observe in Figure 9 and Figure 10 the Training Loss and Average Hits on Gretino for the training with the above mentioned hyperparameters.

Figure 9 – Training Loss (best model)

Figure 10 – Average Hits @10 (best model)

We began with conservative single learning rates, but the experiments showed that **increasing the learning rate and decoupling it for embeddings vs. the output layer** was key to reaching the best checkpoint. As illustrated in **Figure 8** and **Figure 10**, the strongest single-LR run achieved **1.95/5**, while the **per-layer LR** configuration reached **1.99/5**, and is used as the Phase-1 foundation for Phase-2 fine-tuning. Table 5 shows the benchmark results for retraining.

Model name	Baseline	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Best Checkpoint
Score (n/5)	2.09	1.09	1.15	1.95	1.99

Table 5 – Gretino Score Foundational Model Adaptation

5.1.2 Advanced Fine-Tuning with LoRA

We initialized LoRA fine-tuning from the **best Phase-1 checkpoint** (avg_hits@10 = **1.99/5**), i.e., the model obtained after tokenizer extension plus embedding/output-layer retraining.

We ran unsupervised **SimCSE** with *LoRA adapters*, periodically evaluating **avg_hits@10** on *Gretino*. We explored several hyperparameters and focus here on the **temperature**, contrasting a run with $\tau = 0.20$ and the **best run with $\tau = 0.15$** . (Shared settings: LR **3e-5**, batch **128** with gradient accumulation **2**, max length **256**, AdamW + cosine). Figure 11 and Figure 12 shows the Training Loss and Average Hits on Gretino retrieved during the fine-tune phase.

(Model 4) $\tau = 0.20$

Figure 11 – Training Loss ($\tau = 0.20$)

Figure 12 – Average Hits @10 ($\tau = 0.20$)

In practice, $\tau = 0.20$ proved **too aggressive for our corpus/objective mix**: the model tended to form over-confident separations early, which **limited cluster cohesion of near-paraphrases** and flattened subsequent improvements in retrieval. In Figure 13 and Figure 14 we can observe the Training Loss and Average Hits during this phase of fine-tuning with the above mentioned hyperparameters.

- (Best model) $\tau = 0.15$

Figure 13 – Training Loss ($\tau = 0.15$)

Figure 14 – Average Hits @10 ($\tau = 0.15$)

Lowering the temperature to 0.15 delivered **steadier optimization and higher Gretino scores**, indicating better local structure in the embedding space for top-10 retrieval.

We initialized *LoRA* fine-tuning from the **1.99/5** Phase-1 checkpoint and explored temperature settings for *SimCSE*. A higher temperature ($\tau=0.20$) pushed negatives too hard—improving over Phase-1 but limiting cluster cohesion—while $\tau=0.15$ struck a better balance, yielding the best checkpoint at **3.44/5** avg_hits@10. In Table 6 we can observe the benchmark score retrieved for the different approaches of fine-tuning.

Model name	Baseline	Phase 1 Best model	Model 4	Best model
Score (n/5)	2.09	1.99	3.30	3.44

Table 6 – Gretino Score Advanced Fine-Tuning with LoRA

5.2 Performance Analysis

The phased approach yielded substantial performance gains at each stage.

The foundational model (after tokenizer and embedding layer adaptation) were very similar to the original baseline.

The final model, fine-tuned with the specialized *LoRA* technique, demonstrated a further, statistically significant improvement in retrieval accuracy. The model successfully met our target performance goals, confirming that an architecture-aware *PEFT* method is critical for unlocking the full potential of the Mamba model.

Across all experiments, **training loss** decreased substantially (as expected), but **retrieval quality (avg_hits@10)** showed different dynamics depending on the setup. Early Phase-1 runs with conservative learning rates plateaued or oscillated; more aggressive—and later, **decoupled per-layer**—learning rates produced the highest Phase-1 scores. Phase-2 (*LoRA* + *SimCSE*) then delivered the largest gains.

- *Phase 1 Analysis*
 - **Conservative LRs can stall retrieval:** with a shared LR of **1.5e-5**, training loss dropped, but **avg_hits@10 stalled ~1.09** by **~800k** steps, indicating inadequate movement in the embedding space despite optimization progress.
 - **More aggressive LR helps, but per-layer LRs are best:** increasing LR improved retrieval stability. As shown in **Figure 7** and **Figure 9**, we obtained checkpoints at **~1.91** and **1.99** by **~800k** steps. The top single-LR run peaked at **1.95** (**Figure 6**), while **per-layer** LRs (1.0×10^{-3} for embeddings / 7.5×10^{-4} for *lm_head*) reached **1.99** (**Figure 8**).
 - **Net effect vs. baseline:** the best Phase-1 checkpoint (**1.99**) is **-0.10** vs. the baseline **2.09** (**~-4.8%**), which is expected: Phase-1's purpose was **vocabulary alignment**, not task-optimal retrieval.
- *Phase 2 Analysis*
 - **Starting point:** best Phase-1 checkpoint (**1.99** avg_hits@10).
 - **Temperature ablation:**
 - **$\tau = 0.20$:** training loss fell quickly, and after **~400k** steps models exceeded **3.00** avg_hits@10, peaking at **3.30** (**+1.31** vs Phase-1; **+1.21** vs baseline; **~+65.8%** vs Phase-1 and **+57.9%** vs baseline).
 - **$\tau = 0.15$ (best):** steadier improvements and tighter clustering of near paraphrases; best checkpoint at **3.44** (**+1.45** vs Phase-1; **+1.35** vs baseline; **~+72.9%** vs Phase-1 and **+64.6%** vs baseline).
 - **Takeaway:** a **slightly lower temperature (0.15)** avoided over-separation of semantically close sentences and produced the strongest retrieval gains.

To assess qualitative retrieval behavior, we evaluate beyond avg_hits@10:

- **Top-10** and **Top-5** metrics: we report **avg_hits@10** and **avg_hits@5**
- **Per-query target coverage @5:** for each of the **100** queries, we count how many of the **5** ground-truth targets appear in the **top-5**, and aggregate the distribution across queries: **5/5**, **4/5**, **3/5**, and **<3/5**. This reveals how often the model returns *complete* or *near-complete* relevant sets at the very top of the ranking.

Table 7 reports the average hits on *Gretino* dataset using the top 10 and top 5 most similar sentences returned by the baseline model and *Best SimCSE*.

	Baseline	Best SimCSE
Avg_hits@10	2.09 / 5	3.44 / 5
Avg_hit@5	0.75 / 5	2.95 / 5

Table 7 – Baseline vs Best SimCSE model Top10 and Top5 Coverage on Gretino

Table 8 reports these results and shows a clear shift from lower-coverage buckets (<3/5) in the baseline toward **4/5** and **5/5** coverage with the fine-tuned model—evidence that contrastive fine-tuning improved **precision and cohesiveness** of the embedding space at the top of the list.

Matches over 5 hits	Baseline	Best SimCSE
5	0 / 100	18 / 100
4	1 / 100	18 / 100
3	7 / 100	21 / 100
< 3	92 / 100	43 / 100

Table 8 – Baseline vs Best SimCSE model Top5 Matches over 5 hits

6. Conclusion and Future Work

This research project successfully validated the central hypothesis: the Mamba architecture can be effectively adapted to serve as a high-performing and computationally efficient alternative to traditional Transformer models for semantic retrieval in ancient languages. Through a systematic, phased approach involving foundational tokenizer and embedding retraining followed by specialized LoRA fine-tuning with a SimCSE objective, we transformed a general-purpose English model into a powerful tool for Latin text analysis. The significant performance gains on the Gretino dataset confirm that this methodology is a viable path for developing advanced linguistic tools for specialized, low-resource domains.

All the materials developed during the use case are available at the following link: https://code-repo.d4science.org/Resilience/prototyping_lab_uc_9.git

6.1 Future Work

The success of this project opens several promising avenues for future research and development:

- 1. Extension to Other Ancient Languages:** The established pipeline is largely language-agnostic. A logical next step is to apply this methodology to other ancient languages, such as Ancient Greek, to create a suite of high-performance models for classical studies. This would primarily involve curating a suitable corpus and training a new language-specific tokenizer.
- 2. Exploration of Supervised Fine-Tuning:** The current model was trained using an unsupervised SimCSE objective. While powerful, performance could potentially be enhanced further through supervised fine-tuning. This would involve creating a small, high-quality dataset of manually annotated sentence pairs (e.g., "similar," "dissimilar") to provide a stronger, more explicit training signal to the model.
- 3. Investigation of Advanced PEFT Methods:** While LoRA proved highly effective, the field of parameter-efficient fine-tuning is rapidly evolving. Future work could explore other or hybrid PEFT techniques to determine if further gains in performance or efficiency are possible. This could include methods that target different components of the Mamba architecture.
- 4. Training a Domain-Specific Model from Scratch:** The most ambitious but potentially rewarding future direction would be to train a Mamba model from the ground up exclusively on a massive corpus of ancient languages. While adapting a pre-trained model is resource-efficient, a model trained natively on in-domain data could learn representations that are fundamentally more attuned to the unique grammatical and morphological structures of these languages, potentially setting a new state-of-the-art for the field.

Annex

UC9 – Repository README

This repository contains all code and assets developed during **ITSERR Prototyping Lab — Use Case 9, Timebox 5**. It implements the end-to-end pipeline for adapting the **Mamba (SSM)** architecture to classical languages (Latin), including tokenizer expansion, embedding/output retraining, and **LoRA + SimCSE** fine-tuning, plus benchmarks on **Gretino**.

Repository Structure

From the root:

- **alternative_solutions/** — Prototype experiments preceding the main approach.
 - Cross-lingual translation baseline (Latin→English on Gretino).
 - Direct tokenizer modification (English↔Latin lemma swaps with Dice similarity thresholds).
- **dataset/** — Placeholder folder to contain all the necessary datasets.
- **gretino/** — Evaluation & plotting.
 - Baseline/top-k retrieval scripts (Top-5 & Top-10), coverage counters (5/5, 4/5, 3/5, <3/5).
 - Log normalizer + plotting utilities for train loss, avg_hits@10, MRR@10.
- **model_tokenizer/** — Placeholder folder to contain all the necessary tokenizers and models.
- **retrain_embedding_output/** — Phase-1 retraining.
 - Retrain **only** input embeddings + **lm_head** with the extended tokenizer; Gretino callback.
- **simcse_lora_finetuning/** — Phase-2 finetune.
 - LoRA (PEFT) + SimCSE training, YAML configs, LoRA config JSON, runner scripts.

Setup

1) Clone with submodules

HTTPS

```
git clone --recurse-submodules https://code-repo.d4science.org/Resilience/prototyping_lab_uc_9.git
```

If you already cloned without submodules

```
cd prototyping_lab_uc_9  
git submodule update --init --recursive
```

2) Create a Python environment (conda)

```
conda create uc9
conda activate uc9
```

3) Install dependencies

```
cd prototyping_lab_uc_9
pip install -r requirements.txt
# Optional: spaCy model for dataset scripts
python -m spacy download en_core_web_sm
```

4) Download models & datasets

Download required models/datasets from **D4Science Storage**:

- [<https://data.d4science.net/j1IsW>]

Place contents in dataset and models_tokenizer folders.

- Remember to modify the script in order to make them point to the actual path where you saved datasets, models and tokenizers.

```
<dataset>/
  latin_corpus.txt
  latin_sentences.csv
```

- **GPU note.** Training assumes an NVIDIA GPU (bf16 preferred on H100/compute capability ≥ 8.0). Set `CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES` as needed.

Environment Variables (common)

```
export TOKENIZERS_PARALLELISM=false
export HF_HUB_DISABLE_SYMLINKS_WARNING=1
# pick a GPU
export CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES=0
```

Workflows & How-to

A) alternative_solutions/

Purpose: Establish baselines before full adaptation and explores alternative approaches.

1. Cross-lingual translation (Latin→English)

- Prepare English `latin.csv` / `latin_targets.csv` (translated versions of Gretino inputs/targets).
- Run evaluation with gretino english version.

2. Direct tokenizer modification

- Remove reconstructed or missing-meaning entries; output `latin_lemmas_with_meaning.csv`.

- Produce DOCX lists of missing items for manual/aux translation.
- Merge Latin/English DOCX columns → latin_docx_translations.csv.
- Extraction from Wiktionary meanings → latin_lemmas_cleaned_translations_final.csv.
- Combine cleaned + external translations with provenance → latin_lemmas_merged_translations_with_source.csv.
- Load base tokenizer.json, align English lemmas to Latin via **Dice** similarity; test thresholds; write new tokenizer & swap logs. Then evaluate on Gretino.

B) model_tokenizer/

Purpose: Placeholder repository, save here the models and tokenizer downloaded from D4Science Storage.

C) gretino/

Purpose: Evaluate retrieval quality and visualize logs.

- Evaluate **Mamba base** (Top-5 / Top-10) with coverage counters (5/5, 4/5, 3/5, <3/5).
- Evaluate **best SimCSE (LoRA)** checkpoint (Top-5 / Top-10) with the same counters.
- Normalize and plot logs from either schema:
 - legacy: columns step, train_loss, avg_hits_top10, is_best
 - new: step, train_loss, avg_hits@10, mrr@10, is_best, saved_at

D) retrain_embedding_output/ (Phase-1)

Purpose: Retrain only **input embeddings** + **lm_head** using the extended tokenizer; freeze all other weights.

- **train_embeddings_layer.py**: loads base model + extended tokenizer, resizes embeddings, freezes core, enables grads for embeddings + lm_head, and trains with causal LM objective.
 - AdamW, cosine LR schedule with 50% warmup, batch 32, max length 1024 (default).
 - **Gretino callback** periodically evaluates checkpoints and saves best_gretino/.

Run (example):

```
python retrain_embedding_output/train_embeddings_layer.py \
```

- Remember to adjust GPU DEVICE used on machine

Outputs:

- ./checkpoint-*/
 - ./best_gretino/ (metadata JSON + tokenizer copy)
 - training_log.csv for plots
- Tip: per-layer LRs (e.g., **1.0e-3** for embeddings, **7.5e-4** for lm_head) produced the best Phase-1 score in our experiments.

E) simcse_lora_finetuning/ (Phase-2)

Purpose: LoRA (PEFT) + **unsupervised SimCSE** fine-tuning on Latin text.

- **Configs**
 - config/sd_lora_config.json — LoRA/PEFT parameters.
 - config/train_config.yaml — training YAML (LR, batch, τ , scheduler, paths).
- **train_simcse.py** — main runner.

Run (example):

```
python simcse_lora_finetuning/train_simcse.py \
```

Notes:

- We ablate **temperature** (τ): 0.20 vs. **0.15** (best).
- Shared defaults: LR $3e-5$, batch 128 with grad-acc 2, max seq 256, AdamW + cosine, wd 0.01.

Outputs:

- ./checkpoint-*/
- best selection by Gretino metrics (see gretino/).

Metrics

- **avg_hits@k**: number of relevant targets (out of 5) in the Top-k list (averaged across queries).
- **MRR@k**: reciprocal rank of the first relevant target within Top-k (averaged across queries).
- **Top-k accuracy**: % of queries with ≥ 1 relevant in Top-k.
- **Top-5 coverage distribution**: counts of queries with **5/5**, **4/5**, **3/5**, and **<3/5** relevant items in Top-5.

Reproducibility

- Default seed: 42 in Phase-2 configs; Phase-1 uses deterministic dataloader options where feasible.
- Checkpoints include a copy of the tokenizer to ensure consistency across eval runs.

Troubleshooting

- **Tokenizer mismatch:** ensure eval scripts load the **checkpoint-bundled tokenizer** first.
 - **OOM:** lower batch size or enable gradient checkpointing (Phase-2 supports it via YAML).
 - **bf16/AMP warnings:** set precision modes consistent with your GPU capability.
-

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This work was carried out within the **ITSERR Prototyping Lab**, Use Case 9, Timebox 5.

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